

Flexible Scheduling and Wearable Haptics for Human-Robot Collaborative Assembly

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Abstract—This work presents a human-robot collaboration paradigm that goes beyond the pure human-robot coexistence, achieving a flexible and human-aware integration of different operators in a work-cell. A dynamic scheduler able to plan the operations of multiple agents with on-line adaptation to human completion times and flexible management of failures is introduced. Instructions are communicated to the human through visual and haptic cues. In particular, a new tactile communication paradigm based on the association between operations and the portion of workspace in which they are performed is presented. The proposed approach was tested in a realistic human-robot collaboration scenario through an experimental campaign that involved 16 participants.

Index Terms—Human-robot collaboration, wearable haptics, flexible manufacturing, task scheduling

I. INTRODUCTION

Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) has gained increasing attention in the robotics community, as it is expected to add flexibility to industrial manufacturing [1]–[3]. The main idea is to leverage human and robot capabilities to perform different operations during the production process, and achieve a common goal. Today’s collaborative robots, however, are machines that are safe to work with, but are still far from fluently interacting with human co-workers [4], [5].

In this abstract, we summarize a recently published paper [6] in which we address the problem of implementing a HRC paradigm that not only guarantees human safety, but also leads to a seamless, human-aware collaboration. In particular, we tackle two critical aspects: *i*) finding an efficient assignment and schedule of the jobs to be performed by the different agents, and *ii*) communicating the instructions to the human operator in an intuitive and effective way. To address the first point, a novel dynamic scheduler is implemented (Sec. II-A), whereas to address the second, a visuo-haptic interface is used (Sec. II-B). Fig. 1 shows the general principles behind the proposed approach.

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Fig. 1: Proposed HRC paradigm: a dynamic scheduler communicates instructions to the human(s) and to the robot(s), while the agents inform the scheduling algorithm of their state (e.g., operation completion, robot faults).

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Flexible Scheduling Algorithm

The scheduling algorithm introduced in this work leverages a Digital Twin (DT) of the cell, based on Petri Nets (PN) [7], to predict the future evolution of the system and determine the optimal control action with a receding horizon approach. The proposed scheduling algorithm dynamically solves on-line both task allocation and sequencing to adapt the plan to the process variability. It allows the concurrent assembly of multiple products to increase productivity and considers many feasible sequences to complete the assembly. The optimal one for each product is selected in real-time and can change during operation.

Starting from the current DT state, feasible system evolutions are found by exploring the Reachability Tree of the Petri Net over a planning horizon. The optimal schedule is obtained as the sequence of controllable transition firings along the branch with minimum cost. The cost function penalizes the task completion time, the agents’ idle time, and Work-in-Progress parts storage. At each step, commands are sent

Fig. 2: Experimental setup.

to the free resources that start the new operations, the DT state is updated, and the schedule recomputed. This allows adapting to the variability in the duration of human tasks and the occurrence of robot faults.

B. Human-robot interface

As already mentioned, this work aims at creating a bilateral communication among humans and robots, mediated by the scheduler described in Sec. II-A. The scheduler outputs instructions for humans and robots, while agents communicate their state to the scheduler (see Fig. 1). With this information, the scheduler can continue planning the next operations.

From the robot side, communication is enabled by TCP/IP sockets between the CPU running the scheduling algorithm and the robot controller.

From the human side, communication is enabled by the wearable devices shown in Fig. 2. The ring contains three push-buttons and a vibration motor, whereas the bracelets contain two vibration motors each. The communication between the central CPU and the wearable devices is wireless. The buttons on the ring are used to register an input from the user. In our case, the operator presses a button to alert the scheduler about the end of a task. The bracelets, instead, are used to provide the user with information. In particular, vibration patterns indicate the operator's next task or the occurrence of unexpected events. The approach we use to send haptic signals depends on the type of information to be transmitted and mixes typical features of spatial guidance paradigms [8] with techniques to send complex messages through *tactons* [9].

For failures, emergencies, or other operations that require particular attention or immediate intervention, a fast sequence of several vibrations is sent. For assembly operations, the left (right) bracelet vibrates when the human has to work in the left (right) part of the workspace. The number of vibration bursts indicates the sector associated with the starting point of the operation to be performed, where the user should move the hands. The next operation is also displayed to the user through a static image on a screen placed above the workspace (Fig. 2).

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The devised methodology was applied to the collaborative assembly of an emergency button. Performed experiments aimed at *i)* comparing the performance of the dynamic scheduler with that of a static one, and *ii)* evaluating the proposed tactile communication paradigm. In the first set of experiments, we found that the cycle time decreases by 15.6% when using the proposed dynamic scheduler instead of a static one. This is a consequence of the higher adaptability and optimal fault management of the former. In the second set of experiments, we compared two ways of giving instructions to humans, one using only visual information, and one adopting both visual (screen) and tactile (vibrating bracelets) interfaces. The differences, in this case, are more subtle. Through subjective questionnaires filled in by participants, we found that combining vibrotactile and visual inputs to give instructions is the solution that is preferred by users, and is viable even in complex scenarios with many agents and operations. From the analysis of the operators' gaze during experiments, we concluded that more expert users tend to rely more on the haptic interfaces, thus avoiding looking at the screen. This allows them to improve their performance.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work is a first step towards understanding the implications of using vibrotactile feedback in combination with dynamic scheduling for complex collaborative assembly tasks. Obtained results could be extended by studying the visuo-haptic interface more in depth, analyzing, in particular, what is the maximum number of different vibration patterns that users can discriminate and remember without compromising the task execution.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Gilchrist, "Introducing industry 4.0," in *Industry 4.0*. Springer, 2016, pp. 195–215.
- [2] V. Villani, F. Pini, F. Leali, and C. Secchi, "Survey on human-robot collaboration in industrial settings: Safety, intuitive interfaces and applications," *Mechatronics*, 2018.
- [3] A. Ajoudani, A. M. Zanchettin, S. Ivaldi, A. Albu-Schäffer, K. Kosuge, and O. Khatib, "Progress and prospects of the human-robot collaboration," *Autonomous Robots*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 957–975, 2018.
- [4] A. Casalino, C. Messeri, M. Pozzi, A. M. Zanchettin, P. Rocco, and D. Prattichizzo, "Operator awareness in human-robot collaboration through wearable vibrotactile feedback," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 4289–4296, 2018.
- [5] E. Magrini, F. Ferraguti, A. J. Ronga, F. Pini, A. D. Luca, and F. Leali, "Human-robot coexistence and interaction in open industrial cells," *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 61, p. 101846, 2020.
- [6] R. Maderna, M. Pozzi, A. M. Zanchettin, P. Rocco, and D. Prattichizzo, "Flexible scheduling and tactile communication for human-robot collaboration," *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 73, p. 102233, 2022.
- [7] D. Lefebvre and F. Basile, "Design of control sequences for timed petri nets based on tree encoding," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 51, no. 7, pp. 218 – 223, 2018, 14th IFAC Workshop on Discrete Event Systems.
- [8] S. Scheggi, M. Aggravi, and D. Prattichizzo, "Cooperative navigation for mixed human-robot teams using haptic feedback," *IEEE Trans. on Human-Machine Systems*, vol. 47, no. 4, pp. 462–473, 2017.
- [9] L. A. Jones and N. Sarter, "Tactile displays: Guidance for their design and application," *Human Factors*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 90–111, 2008.